

Sample Name: PP Vir 5-10 μm

Material: Polypropylene

Size: 5-10 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 4,19 μm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- $1,8 \times 10^{13}$ particles per gram
- 37992 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% C_3H_6 (PP) determined by XRF
- No changes due to milling or aging observed in FTIR spectrum
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PP spectrum

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50_v} : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50_N} : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
6,51	1,75	0,36	0,18	0,14	4,19	1.8×10^{13}	37992

Chemical Composition* (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
C ₃ H ₆	99,937
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Si	227
P	73
S	10
Cl	449
K	54
Ca	88
Ti	3
Cr	83
Mn	4
Fe	223
Ni	15
Cu	1
Zn	1
Mo	1
Pb	1

* The XRF results shown were measured on PP UV-aged material.

Chemical Bonding (Using µ-FTIR provided by TNO)

Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (provided by TNO)